

Supplementary File 1

Additional Table 1: Association between PCOS status and frequency of fruits consumption among respondents. Results are expressed as odds ratios (OR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI) obtained from a generalized ordered logistic regression model.

Variable	Category	OR	95% CI	P value
PCOS Status	No	Ref	-	-
	Yes	0.93	[0.64,1.35]	0.714
Age	23-26	Ref	-	-
	15-18	2.60	[1.22, 5.52]	0.013
	19-22	1.17	[0.71, 1.95]	0.522
	27-30	0.83	[0.517, 1.338]	0.447
Education	Secondary/Higher	Ref	-	-
	Secondary			
	No/Primary	0.44	[0.25, 0.78]	0.005
	Graduate or higher	2.42	[1.531, 3.832]	0.000
Employment	Employed	Ref	-	-
	Student	1.67	[0.96, 2.90]	0.066
	Homemaker	1.42	[0.87, 2.31]	0.154
BMI	Normal	Ref	-	-
	Under weight	0.44	[0.25, 0.79]	0.006
	Over weight	1.03	[0.71, 1.50]	0.843
Marital Status	Married	Ref	-	-
	Unmarried	0.51	[0.31, 0.84]	0.008

Additional Table 2: Association between PCOS status and frequency of vegetable consumption among respondents. Results are expressed as odds ratios (OR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI) obtained from a generalized ordered logistic regression model.

Variable	Category	OR	95% CI	P value
PCOS Status	No	Ref	–	–
	Yes	0.76	[0.50, 1.14]	0.184
Age	23–26	Ref	–	–
	15–18	0.91	[0.41, 2.02]	0.816
	19–22	0.57	[0.33, 0.99]	0.045
	27–30	1.71	[1.00, 2.95]	0.052
Education	Secondary/Higher Secondary	Ref	–	–
	No/Primary	0.37	[0.20, 0.69]	0.002
	Graduate or higher	0.8	[0.48, 1.33]	0.383
Employment	Employed	Ref	–	–
	Student	0.65	[0.36, 1.20]	0.168
	Homemaker	0.1	[0.02, 0.64]	0.015
BMI	Normal	Ref	–	–
	Under weight	0.25	[0.14, 0.46]	0.001
	Over weight	0.8	[0.53, 1.20]	0.278
Marital Status	Married	Ref	–	–
	Unmarried	0.07	[0.01, 0.42]	0.004

Additional Table 3: Association between PCOS status and frequency of meat consumption among respondents. Results are expressed as odds ratios (OR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI) obtained from a generalized ordered logistic regression model.

Variable	Category	OR	95% CI	p-value
PCOS Status	No	Ref	–	–
	Yes	0.84	[0.56, 1.25]	0.379
Age	23–26	Ref	–	–
	15–18	2.02	[0.88, 4.64]	0.100
	19–22	1.33	[0.76, 2.32]	0.316
	27–30	1.53	[0.91, 2.56]	0.106
Education	Secondary/Higher Sec.	Ref	–	–
	No/Primary	0.44	[0.23, 0.83]	0.012
	Graduate or higher	1.33	[0.80, 2.20]	0.272
Employment	Employed	Ref	–	–
	Student	1.14	[0.63, 2.06]	0.660
	Homemaker	0.63	[0.37, 1.07]	0.089
BMI Status	Normal	Ref	–	–
	Under weight	0.92	[0.49, 1.72]	0.790
	Over weight	1.29	[0.86, 1.92]	0.216
Marital Status	Married	Ref	–	–
	Unmarried	0.67	[0.40, 1.11]	0.118

Additional Table 4: Association between PCOS status and frequency of fish consumption among respondents. Results are expressed as odds ratios (OR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI) obtained from a generalized ordered logistic regression model.

Variable	Category	OR	95% CI	p-value
PCOS Status	No	Ref	–	–
	Yes	1.61	[1.09, 2.37]	0.017
Age	23–26	Ref	–	–
	15–18	1.58	[0.71, 3.50]	0.258
	19–22	0.47	[0.28, 0.81]	0.006
	27–30	1.42	[0.86, 2.35]	0.170
Education	Secondary/Higher Sec.	Ref	–	–
	No/Primary	0.23	[0.08, 0.64]	0.005
	Graduate or higher	0.24	[0.10, 0.54]	0.001
Employment	Employed	Ref	–	–
	Student	0.72	[0.41, 1.27]	0.261
	Homemaker	0.52	[0.31, 0.87]	0.013
BMI Status	Normal	Ref	–	–
	Under weight	1.05	[0.58, 1.88]	0.880
	Over weight	1.06	[0.72, 1.57]	0.774
Marital Status	Married	Ref	–	–
	Unmarried	0.36	[0.22, 0.59]	0.001

Additional Table 5: Association between PCOS status and frequency of fast food consumption among respondents. Results are expressed as odds ratios (OR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI) obtained from a generalized ordered logistic regression model.

Variable	Category	OR	95% CI	p-value
PCOS Status	No	Ref	–	–
	Yes	0.6	[0.41, 0.87]	0.007
Age	23–26	Ref	–	–
	15–18	0.96	[0.45, 2.04]	0.907
	19–22	1.62	[0.98, 2.67]	0.062
	27–30	1.13	[0.69, 1.86]	0.630
Education	Secondary/Higher Sec.	Ref	–	–
	No/Primary	1.11	[0.60, 2.03]	0.741
	Graduate or higher	1.06	[0.66, 1.69]	0.805
Employment	Employed	Ref	–	–
	Student	0.89	[0.52, 1.54]	0.679
	Homemaker	0.47	[0.28, 0.78]	0.004
BMI Status	Normal	Ref	–	–
	Under weight	1.57	[0.89, 2.78]	0.122
	Over weight	1.3	[0.89, 1.89]	0.175
Marital Status	Married	Ref	–	–
	Unmarried	1.88	[1.17, 3.02]	0.010

Additional Table 6: Association between PCOS status and frequency of dairy products consumption among respondents. Results are expressed as odds ratios (OR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI) obtained from a generalized ordered logistic regression model.

Variable	Category	OR	95% CI	p-value
PCOS Status	No	Ref	–	–
	Yes	0.37	[0.25, 0.54]	0.001
Age	23–26	Ref	–	–
	15–18	2.57	[1.18, 5.57]	0.017
	19–22	0.69	[0.40, 1.17]	0.167
	27–30	1.38	[0.85, 2.24]	0.190
Education	Secondary/Higher Sec.	Ref	–	–
	No/Primary	1.1	[0.62, 1.95]	0.750
	Graduate or higher	0.7	[0.44, 1.13]	0.144
Employment	Employed	Ref	–	–
	Student	0.45	[0.25, 0.81]	0.008
	Homemaker	0.76	[0.46, 1.25]	0.276
BMI Status	Normal	Ref	–	–
	Under weight	0.99	[0.56, 1.73]	0.967
	Over weight	1	[0.67, 1.47]	0.984
Marital Status	Married	Ref	–	–
	Unmarried	1.9	[1.14, 3.19]	0.014

Additional Table 7: Association between PCOS status and frequency of carbonated beverage consumption among respondents. Results are expressed as odds ratios (OR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI) obtained from a generalized ordered logistic regression model.

Variable	Category	OR	95% CI	p-value
PCOS Status	No	Ref	–	–
	Yes	0.7	[0.45, 1.09]	0.115
Age	23–26	Ref	–	–
	15–18	0.65	[0.26, 1.59]	0.343
	19–22	0.88	[0.50, 1.57]	0.671
	27–30	0.64	[0.34, 1.18]	0.150
Education	Secondary/Higher Sec.	Ref	–	–
	No/Primary	1.12	[0.56, 2.27]	0.747
	Graduate or higher	0.86	[0.51, 1.47]	0.589
Employment	Employed	Ref	–	–
	Student	2.09	[1.05, 4.18]	0.036
	Homemaker	1.12	[0.59, 2.12]	0.733
BMI Status	Normal	Ref	–	–
	Under weight	1.09	[0.56, 2.12]	0.801
	Over weight	1.54	[0.98, 2.40]	0.059
Marital Status	Married	Ref	–	–
	Unmarried	0.92	[0.51, 1.66]	0.787

Additional Table 8: Association between PCOS status and frequency of tea/coffee consumption among respondents. Results are expressed as odds ratios (OR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI) obtained from a generalized ordered logistic regression model.

Variable	Category	OR	95% CI	p-value
PCOS Status	No	Ref	–	–
	Yes	0.45	[0.31, 0.66]	0.001
Age	23–26	Ref	–	–
	15–18	0.7	[0.32, 1.51]	0.359
	19–22	0.76	[0.46, 1.28]	0.305
	27–30	1.32	[0.81, 2.15]	0.272
Education	Secondary/Higher Sec.	Ref	–	–
	No/Primary	1.55	[0.88, 2.74]	0.131
	Graduate or higher	0.98	[0.60, 1.60]	0.938
Employment	Employed	Ref	–	–
	Student	0.93	[0.53, 1.66]	0.816
	Homemaker	1.38	[0.83, 2.29]	0.211
BMI Status	Normal	Ref	–	–
	Under weight	1.09	[0.60, 2.01]	0.772
	Over weight	1.61	[1.09, 2.37]	0.017
Marital Status	Married	Ref	–	–
	Unmarried	3.05	[1.84, 5.07]	0.001

Additional Table 9: Association between PCOS status and frequency of water consumption among respondents. Results are expressed as odds ratios (OR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI) obtained from a generalized ordered logistic regression model.

Variable	Category	OR	95% CI	p-value
PCOS Status	No	Ref	–	–
	Yes	0.96	[0.66, 1.39]	0.831
Age	23–26	Ref	–	–
	15–18	1.23	[0.57, 2.67]	0.596
	19–22	0.5	[0.27, 0.93]	0.029
	27–30	0.77	[0.47, 1.24]	0.278
Education	Secondary/Higher Sec.	Ref	–	–
	No/Primary	1.27	[0.71, 2.26]	0.422
	Graduate or higher	2.04	[1.28, 3.26]	0.003
Employment	Employed	Ref	–	–
	Student	0.59	[0.34, 1.02]	0.059
	Homemaker	0.89	[0.54, 1.45]	0.637
BMI Status	Normal	Ref	–	–
	Under weight	0.45	[0.25, 0.81]	0.008
	Over weight	0.96	[0.66, 1.39]	0.819
Marital Status	Married	Ref	–	–
	Unmarried	1.04	[0.64, 1.67]	0.881